

FACTORS INFLUENCING CUSTOMER BEHAVIOR TOWARDS ONLINE SHOPPING: EVIDENCE BASED ON UNDERGRADUATES IN SRI LANKA

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Introduction

Background of the Research Study

Over the course of two decades, the Internet has played a critical role in various aspects, and today, without the Internet, the current generation does not know life (Jawa & Chaichi, 2015). The rise of internet usage has created a new phenomenon of consumer behaviour, in which the consumers' attention has been shifted to online shopping. Online shopping not only provides consumers with comfort and other benefits, but also provides a tremendous service to corporate organizations (Jawa & Chaichi, 2015). Furthermore, increasing numbers of organizations are moving from bricks to clicks due to fresh possibilities and difficulties that have appeared on the market (Jawa & Chaichi, 2015). Online shopping has therefore evidently become the fresh company trend of the twenty-first century (Jawa & Chaichi, 2015). Even though e-commerce, especially internet shopping, has grown globally in latest years (Sam & Sharma, 2015), some developing nations like Sri Lanka are still lagging behind global development in this respect. However, there is a tendency to use online shopping platform to meet their purchasing needs among new generation. Further, online shopping in Sri Lanka has been rapidly developing and has the ability to grow exponentially in the future as internet penetration spreads far and wide across rural regions. Furthermore, e-commerce transactions in Sri Lanka are expected to grow by more than 72% in the near future. (Athapaththu & Kulathunga, 2018).

Problem Statement

Even in Sri Lanka, online shopping has a rapid influence on people's lifestyles. Sri Lankans continued to subscribe to 24.43 million cellular phone links and over 300,000 broadband and dial-up web connections during 2018. It has increased the web penetration to 30% and the total web users to 6.1 million (Telecommunications Regulatory Commission of Sri Lanka, 2020). Further, online shopping through social networks gradually captures the participation of young people. Revenue in the e-commerce market in Sri Lanka is US\$1,395m and this revenue is expected to show an annual growth rate of 17.2% by 2025 (Statista, 2021). Although usage of the internet is high in Sri Lanka, usage of the internet for online shopping is lagging from the customer perspective. Though, there are many online platforms offering online shopping such as eBay, Alibaba, and DARAZ, the usage is very lacking. This arises the research question; What factors determine consumers online purchasing behaviours?

Several studies have been conducted to identify the factors influence on online shopping. However, majority of them are done for other countries. Online shopping is a behavioural phenomenon and it varies among different cultures and context. Therefore, finding of other countries may not be applicable to the Sri Lankan context. Because of that, identifying factors is very important for the Sri Lankan context. This research helps to identify factors affecting customer behaviour towards online shopping in Sri Lanka. This study was designed to determine the relationship between customer behaviour and influencing factors that are related to online shopping within the Sri Lankan context.

Research Objectives

- ❖ To identify the factors influencing customer behaviour towards online shopping in Sri Lanka.
- ❖ To identify the relationship between the influencing factors and the buying behaviour of customers.

Methodology

Conceptual Framework of the study

The conceptual model was developed based on the literature review. Literature review revealed that consumer satisfaction, perceived usefulness, website design quality and perceived trust are the key determinant of the Consumers' Online Buying Behaviour. Therefore, this study proposed following conceptual model and hypotheses for this study.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

The following hypotheses were formed to test the relationship between variables.

H1: There is a positive relationship between customer satisfaction and online shopping behaviour

H2: There is a positive relationship between perceived usefulness and online shopping behaviour.

H3: There is a positive relationship between web site quality and online shopping behaviour.

H4: There is a positive relationship between perceived trust and online shopping behaviour.

The above-mentioned variables were measured by adopting the items from the literatures.

Design of the study

This study used the deductive approach and it was a quantitative cross-sectional study. Conceptual model and the hypotheses were developed based on the literature. All items of the variables were adapted from the literature. The population for this study was all consumers in Sri Lanka. However, due to the impracticability of testing all the consumers in Sri Lanka, this study chose the Sri Lankan University, undergraduates. University students are very keen on technology and represent the youth in Sri Lanka. Further, they are heavy users of technology for their life activities. Therefore, data were collected from management undergraduate from one of the government universities in Sri Lanka. According to the ex-ante power analysis tool minimum required sample size for 0.05 probability level was 91. Data were collected through online questionnaire and data were analysed through descriptive analysis, validity and reliability testing and finally, hypotheses testing using SmartPLS 3 software.

Results and Discussion

Descriptive analysis

Total of 91 responses were received and 56% of them were female respondents and 44% them were male respondents. Majority of the respondents (67%) use internet over four years and only 3 respondents use

internet under the 6 months. Rest of the respondents use internet in between six months and four years.

Reliability and Validity Analysis

All the items loadings, all Cronbach’s Alpha and Composite reliability values are greater than 0.7 as suggested by Hair et al. (2011) and thus the indicator reliability and internal consistency was established in this research (Hair et al., 2011). As suggested by Hair et al. (2011), all the AVE values are greater than 0.5 and thus Convergent validity was demonstrated (Hair et al., 2011). Further, none of the constructs’ cross-correlations exceeded the respective square root of each construct’s AVE thus discriminant validity was also demonstrated in this research (Hair et al., 2011).

Hypothesis Testing

After establishing the validity and reliability of this research, relationship was tested using structural model analysis. As can be shown in Table 1, the results showed that perceived usefulness and perceived trust has positive impact on online shopping behaviour and thus H2 and H4 were accepted. However, customer satisfaction and website quality did not have an effect on online shopping behaviour.

Table 1. Summary of the Hypotheses Testing

Hypotheses	Path Coefficient	P Value	Result
H1: There is a positive relationship between customer satisfaction and online shopping behaviour	0.214	0.162	Not Supported
H2: There is a positive relationship between perceived usefulness and online shopping behaviour.	0.335	0.046	Supported
H3: There is a positive relationship between web site quality and online shopping behaviour.	0.106	0.409	Not Supported

H4: There is a positive relationship between perceived trust and online shopping behaviour.	0.286	0.006	Supported
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The main findings were as follows.

Hypothesis 1: There is a positive relationship between consumer satisfaction and online shopping behaviour.

As shown in the table 1, there was no enough evidence to say consumer satisfaction of Use has a significant positive impact on online shopping behaviour (0.214, $P < 0.162$). This means there is no enough evidence to prove that consumer satisfaction is impacting the online shopping behaviour in the undergraduates.

Hypothesis 2: There is a positive relationship between perceived usefulness and online shopping behaviour.

As shown in table perceived usefulness would have a significant impact on online shopping behaviour (0.335, $P < 0.046$). This indicates that the undergraduates, who had perceived usefulness has tendency to do online shopping.

Hypothesis 3: There is a positive relationship between web site quality and online shopping behaviour.

As shown in the table there was no enough evidence to say web site design quality would have a significant impact on online shopping behaviour (0.106, $P < 0.409$). This indicates that there was no enough evidence to prove the positive relationship between web site quality and online shopping behaviour.

Hypothesis 4: There is a positive relationship between perceived trust and online shopping behaviour.

As per the table above, it proves that Perceived trust has a significant positive impact on online shopping behaviour (0.286, $P < 0.006$). This

indicates that Perceived trust positively impacts on online shopping behaviour.

Conclusion

The first objective of this research was to identify the factors that influence on online shopping behaviour. Though literature suggests four key determinants, the empirical study revealed that only the perceived usefulness and perceived trust are the determinant of online shopping behaviour in this research context. With regards to the second objective, both perceived usefulness and perceived trust has positive impact on online shopping behaviour respectively and it was 0.335, 0.286.

Limited sample size is a one of the limitations of this study. This study limits to the management undergraduates in one of Sri Lankan universities. Similarly, this study was limited to most cited four determinants. Therefore, there is a further research opportunity on studying the same issue using range of determinant factors and using a large sample size. Further, it would be interesting to conduct a survey at another university. If this is done and similar results are discovered, one could apply generalizability to the results.

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